

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy on Abstract Creative-Thinking Skill in Basic Science among Secondary School Students in Gboko, Benue State

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹

Email: ayuageoffrey@gmail.com,

Gamat, Grace Bala²

Email: gracegamatnendi@gmail.com,

Agbidye, Anna³

Email: annagbidye@gmail.com

Terhemba, Wisdom Kwaghfan⁴

Email: kwatexwisdom@gmail.com

^{1,3&4}Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria

Abstract

Effect of Creative-Teaching strategy on abstract creative-thinking skill in basic science was investigated using pretest and post-test quasi experimental research design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. A multistage sample of 70 (34 males and 36 females) students was drawn from two intact classes of a population of 674 (356 male and 318 female) students in all government secondary schools (government grant aided schools only) in Gboko, Benue state, during the 2021/2022 academic session. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking instrument with reliability coefficient of 0.83 was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic. Data were analyzed using mean and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings showed no significant difference in the ACT among varied-ability students within the teaching methods, $F(2, 63) = 0.319, p(0.728) > 0.05$. However, those taught Basic Science using CT exhibited significantly higher ACS than those taught using Lecture Method. $F(1, 63) = 39.117, p(0.000) < 0.05$. Moreso, no significant difference existed in the students' ACS based on gender $F(2, 28) = 0.791, p(0.463) > 0.05$. It was concluded that abstract creative-thinking skill among varied-ability students was enhanced without gender disparity, if Basic Science is taught using Creative Teaching. Therefore, Creative Teaching was recommended for teaching science at the basic education level.

Keywords: Creative-Teaching (CT), Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS), Basic Science, Varied-ability and Gender.

Introduction

Education is the strength, wealth for national building and above all a key instrument to make learners at basic, post-basic and tertiary education to live and flourish in the 21st century. Also, the global community wants people who have the capacity that could face thought-provoking socio-economic situations and could solve up-to-date unemployment, poverty and pandemic problems. It is important to note that one of these capabilities is Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS), which is an aspect of creative thinking. Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS) refers to the degree beyond labelling; based on an idea that creativity requires an abstraction of thought (Terhemba et al., 2023). Creativity is an indescribable idea, hitherto it creates a significant facet of daily living. Therefore, as teaching methods and resources are the bases of effective classroom instruction, science objectives as incorporated in the policy document on education in Nigeria can be boosted through creativity that encompasses the nature of ACS which may lead to cultivating productivity into students at the basic education level. Basic education level is the foundational class to which any further study of sciences can be built and if students at this level are nurtured with ACS, hopefully productivity, economic growth, development and sustainability may have its course since science has to do with our environment.

Science is a creative endeavour of the human mind. To understand the natural world, scientists discover new problems, think of multiple ways to approach problems, come up with hypotheses, figure out how to collect meaningful data, explain

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

those data, and come up with new theories (Peng, 2019). Those scientific thinking processes require creative thinking such as the application of analogy, metaphor, brainstorming, lateral thinking, imagination and all these may have to do with abstract thinking. An example of how scientists used creative thinking during scientific discovery, for instance, the wave theory of light was derived from an analogy between light and sound, the idea that the earth was a giant magnet and was created from many shared properties between the planet earth and magnet (Peng, 2019). Scientists develop new and useful ideas, which correspond to the description of abstract creative thinking that may yield productivity and sustainability. Therefore, it is unquestionable that science for productivity and sustainability maybe real if students gain abstract creative thinking through creative teaching.

Creative Teaching (CT) is tending to create classroom instruction excellently and in a novel style, teaching creatively and teaching for creativity. Creative-teaching of Basic Science refers to demonstrating how to think skilfully amidst tactics, resources in Basic Science content for inspiring learning and fostering students' creativity using Torrance incubation model and exhibiting creative-teaching behaviours (Ayua & Eriba, 2023). Ismail et al (2018) viewed it as involving teachers making learning more interesting and effective; using imaginative approaches or exhibiting the behaviours during lessons. It involves teachers making learning more interesting and effective and using imaginative approaches or exhibiting Creative Teaching Behaviours (CTB) during science classroom interactions (Suhvan; Cremin as cited in Terhemba, 2022) and giving room for effective teaching and learning to occur among different ability learners in science education. This could be why McFinn (2015) confirmed that it is based on individuals' needs and abilities, which need freedom in learning as an active mode that influences innovative personality development, which creates something exceptional and turns it into an entrepreneurial activity for productivity and ensuing sustainability.

There are several creative teaching models which include Misutova's (2003) as cited in Ayua (2021) Creative-Teaching Model which was developed for mathematics and technical courses of basic study at the university level; and Schnapp's (2018) Creativity Pedagogical Model which is targeted for teachers and education institutions. However, Torrance Incubation Model (TIM) of creative teaching and learning which can be applied at any level of education was emphasized and adopted for this study. TIM of creative teaching and learning is a 3-stage (heightening anticipation, deepening expectations and keeping it going) model for delivering both subject and content. According to Torrance and Safter (as cited in, Terhemba, 2022), the model was designed to make teaching more effective in any subject at any age. TIM of creative teaching and learning can be applied to a lesson unit or project in any subject including Basic Science at the upper-basic school level with varied-ability students. Torrance (as cited in Ayua, et al., 2022) believed that people are inquisitive, exploring and searching kind of beings. Similarly, Bruner's (1960) theory of intellectual development, which states that learning is best through discovery and interaction with mental development advancing from non-abstract to abstract alongside age. It holds that knowledge via discovery is fundamental to learning and emphasizes that learning is by doing and thinking creatively. So, when given a choice, students would choose to learn creatively. They would continue to find problems and cannot keep from digging into things, turning ideas over in their minds, trying out new combinations, searching for new relationships and struggling for new, unique and abstract insights. Therefore, the link between this theory and creative teaching is linked to examine, if it could inculcate ACT to harness scientific creative-thinking knowledge for productivity and sustainability among varied-ability students in Basic Science.

Creative-thinking is the ability to come up with novel ideas and turn such ideas generated into fashionable, unique products for human use. Creativity is the interaction among aptitude, process, and environment by which an individual or group produces a perceptible product that is both novel and useful (Plucker & Begetto, as cited in Irugalbandara, 2020). A process of becoming understanding to problems, lacks, gaps in knowledge, missing essentials, conflicts, and so on; finding the difficulty; searching for answers, making guesses, or framing suggestions about the deficiencies; testing and retesting these hypotheses and possibly modifying and retesting them, and finally communicating the results (Torrance, as cited in Terhemba, 2022). It is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. Therefore, Torrance (as cited in Irugalbandara, 2020) identified what he termed five main elements of creative thinking: fluency, flexibility, elaboration, originality and abstractness of titles. To this end, abstractness of titles also known as abstract creative thinking was used for this study.

Abstract creative thinking has to do with Basic Science male and female students with varied-ability to think beyond normal description of available resources, items, problems and/or products. That is why Ng and Lee (2019) affirmed that it is the ability to go beyond a concrete physical description. Abstract creative thinking which goes beyond simple description relates to the subjects by synthesizing, organizing processes and thinking creatively with resources. At the highest level, there is an ability to capture the essence of the information involved, to know what is important, and to enable the viewer to see available resources more deeply and richly, where male and female students with varied-ability may use abstract creative

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

thinking that go beyond simple description and communicate something unique about resources (Scholastic Testing Service, 2018). With this unusual trait required for carrying out successful entrepreneurial venture, if truly integrated in the classroom instruction, it may perhaps be assumed that male and female Basic Science students with varied-ability at the basic education level could think abstractly when posed with resources for productivity and keeping it going sustainability may have its course. Varied-ability in one way or the other is as old as man and cut across all areas of life including students' ability levels and Basic Science students at the basic education level not been an exception. Ability grouping according to Ikyernum (2022) is the practice of assigning students into different educational groups based on past academic performance and it is used synonymously with tracking and streaming of school learners. Maikano (2016) maintains that ability grouping is based on educators' judgments of students' abilities; and that when assigning students' to tracks, prior test scores or other performance measures provided from other grades or schools are used to determine the ability levels. In this study, Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2018) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2018), grading system with six performance grades (A-F) was used for the students into: High Ability Level (HAL) = A (75-100%) and B (65-74%); Average Ability Level (AAL) = C (55-64%) and D (45-54%); and Low Ability Level (LAL) = E (40-44%) and F (0-39%).

Gender variance is as old as the world and has been used severally in academic discourse. It is the nature of being masculine or feminine; gentleman or lady; lad or girl. Gender disparity according to Danjuma (2015) globally militates against equitable participation of boys and girls in science education especially in Africa. Ali et al (2014) submitted that females face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in participation in the sciences. United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation - UNESCO as cited in Ikyernum (2022), females from over 50% of the world's active population make immense contributions to development, although they still face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in participation in the science subjects. With such discourse, it is pertinent to look at previous empirical whether creative teaching on creativity is male and female with varied-ability biased or unbiased.

Ng and Lee (2019) investigated creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance tests of creative thinking and found that the students tended to be good at producing a large number of relevant abstract thinking (abstractness of titles dimension) ideas. Similarly, Özgenel et al (2019) explored Creative Thinking of Hong Kong Undergraduate Students Using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking and found that the enriched workshop trainings given to the students have affected and developed the students' creative thinking skills (abstractness of titles inclusively) positively. Marzieh and Nesa (2016) examined Comparison of Creativity Dimensions between bilingual elementary students in Fervan City, Iran and found that the dimensions from creativity were significantly different between the two groups of bilingual students. Similarly, Midilli et al. (2022) examined Turkish gifted primary school students' creative thinking skills and found that in the abstractness of titles sub-dimension of students who received pre-school education scored significantly higher than the students who did not receive pre-school education and there was no significant difference between the scores of the students in TTCT based on gender. Moreso, Madar et al. (2019) facilitating Torrance Test of Creative Thinking in Malaysian TVET research: the initial step of inter-rater reliability determination indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were at an excellent level and not significantly different based on gender. Ulger and Morsunbul (2017) examined differences in creative thinking aspect: comparison of male and female students in Turkish university students and found that there was a significant difference between male and female university students on creative thinking skills in favour of female.

The previous study's findings used Torrance Test of Creative thinking (TTCT), creative thinking skills with different teaching methods and found useful results, however, gap still exist. These studies did not use TIM of creative teaching, the studies failed to consider students at basic education level with varied-ability and the studies were geographically limited to Nigeria. Therefore, there is the need to examine whether creative teaching could enhance one of these aspects of creativity among varied-ability students in Gboko. Creativity is an element like gold for functioning of children, young people, the old even the society at large, making it a necessary factor in a balanced and democratic education system and the global society in the 21st century for productivity and sustainability. Rosenstock and Riordan (2017) highlighted the role of creativity as a key disposition necessary in a modern, innovation economy, characterised by global and rapid change. In a similar vein, Bakhshi et al (2017) reported that skills such as creative problem solving, and also abilities including abstractness of titles, will be amongst those in extreme demand in future workforce. However, there is a problem between policy and practice due to poor teaching methods. Ayua and Agbidye (2020) established that the gap between policy and practice is occasioned by poor teaching methods resulting in unemployment due to lack of entrepreneurial creativity for self-reliance after school. Since the global economy is shifting to a new paradigm which people may be expected to have creativity skills, it is therefore, vital to

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

develop new skills like abstract creative thinking in students. It is against this background that effect of creative-teaching strategy on abstract creative-thinking skill in basic science among secondary school students in Gboko, Benue state was studied.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were examined to:

1. Determine the Abstract Creative-thinking (ACS) of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT) and Lecture Method (LM).
2. Find the ACS of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference in ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM?
2. What is the mean difference in ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ α -level:

1. There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM.
2. There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used for this study. After pre-test, the experimental group was taught the topic “chemicals” using Creative Teaching (CT); while the control group was taught the same concept using Lecture Method (LM) for six weeks before post-test. This was to enhanced abstract creative thinking by producing unimaginable, novel, and unique product through abstract thinking. A multistage sample of 70 (34 males and 36 females) students was drawn from two intact classes of a population of 674 (356 males and 318 females) students in all government secondary schools (government grant aided schools only) in Gboko, Benue state in Benue state, during the 2021/2022 academic session. Firstly, the schools were stratified into two (2-single schools with 290 students and 5-mixed schools with 384 students). Secondly, the five schools were purposively selected (4 in Gboko-North and 1 in Gboko South) and this was because, the schools were co-educational. Creativity equivalence test was administered to the students in the five schools and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine students’ ACS homogeneity and equivalence. Out of the five schools, four schools in Gboko North had homogeneity and equivalence TTCT scores. To determine the Experimental and control group, the researcher casted a lot (A= Experimental Group, B = Control Group, C = Not involved in any group and D = None of the above) for the four schools since the four were homogeneous. Thirdly, the two schools that had correct draw from the lot, students in each of the schools were randomly assigned into 35 experimental and 35 control groups. This was for the purpose of honesty, objectivity, ensuring a bias-free sampling and assignment of subjects into groups.

Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section “A” collected students’ bio data; while section ‘B’ had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students’ ACS in Basic Science. Students’ ability levels were determined based on previous term’s performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). TTCT-Figural B was validated by two experts: a senior lecturer in Mathematics Education and a Professor of Chemistry, both from the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi. The instrument was pilot tested on 15 Basic II students in one of the schools in Gboko other than the sample for the main study. A reliability coefficient of 0.83 was determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistic. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using two-way Analysis of Covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, data measured based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

Results

Research Question One

What is the mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM?

Table 1: ACS Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching (CT) and those Taught using Lecture Method (LM).

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Teaching Method	TTCT-Pretest		TTCT-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	14	CT	2.04	1.480	4.93	1.678	2.89	2.51
	14	LM	2.80	1.917	2.42	1.384	0.38	
Average	9	CT	3.29	2.088	3.62	1.787	0.33	0.12
	11	LM	1.72	0.930	1.51	1.075	0.21	
Low	12	CT	2.27	1.029	4.47	2.529	2.20	1.83
	10	LM	1.84	0.901	1.47	1.313	0.37	
Cluster		CT	2.53		4.34		1.81	1.49
		LM	2.12		1.80		0.32	

The result in Table 1 shows the pre-test ACS mean scores among varied-ability students, between CT and LM with cluster means of 2.53 and 2.12. The Table also shows that all the ACT mean scores among varied-ability students in the CT were higher than those in the LM with cluster mean gain difference of 1.49.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT?

Table 2: ACS Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught Basic Science using Creative Teaching.

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Gender	TTCT-Pretest		TTCT-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	5	Male	1.24	0.868	5.36	1.717	4.12	1.91
	9	Female	2.48	1.602	4.69	1.709	2.21	
Average	7	Male	3.10	2.273	3.11	1.917	0.01	0.86
	4	Female	3.63	1.991	4.50	1.291	0.87	
Low	6	Male	2.33	0.999	4.62	2.550	2.29	0.22
	4	Female	2.18	1.220	4.25	2.872	2.07	
Cluster		Male	2.22		4.36		2.14	0.42
		Female	2.76		4.48		1.72	

The result in Table 2 shows the pre-test ACS mean scores among varied-ability levels between male and female students with cluster means of 2.22 and 2.76. The table also shows that the ACS mean scores in the post test between male and female students with cluster mean gains of 2.14 and 1.72 respectively.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT and LM.

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

Table 3: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on ACS among Varied-ability Levels Based on Teaching Methods.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	130.476 ^a	6	21.746	7.693	.000	.423
Intercept	206.544	1	206.544	73.065	.000	.537
Pre TTCT	1.129	1	1.129	.399	.530	.006
Teaching Method	110.578	1	110.578	39.117	.000	.383
Varied Ability	15.252	2	7.626	2.698	.075	.079
Teaching Method * Varied Ability	1.805	2	.903	.319	.728	.010
Error	178.092	63	2.827			
Total	991.850	70				
Corrected Total	308.569	69				

a. R Squared = .423 (Adjusted R Squared = .368)

The result in Table 3 shows no significant difference in the ACS among varied-ability students within those taught Basic Science using CT and those taught using LM, $F(2, 63) = 0.319, p(0.728) > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. However, the table showed that student's ACS in the CT was better than those in the LM $F(1, 63) = 39.117, p(0.000) < 0.05$. The implication of this result is that, although creative teaching enhances ACS, it is not dependent on students' academic ability.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean difference in the ACS scores of male and female students with varied-ability taught Basic Science using CT.

Table 4: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on ACS among Varied-ability Levels Based on Gender.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	17.602 ^a	6	2.934	.689	.660	.129
Intercept	161.736	1	161.736	37.991	.000	.576
Pre TTCT	.267	1	.267	.063	.804	.002
Gender	.055	1	.055	.013	.910	.000
Varied Ability	8.328	2	4.164	.978	.389	.065
Gender * Varied Ability	6.737	2	3.369	.791	.463	.053
Error	119.201	28	4.257			
Total	810.010	35				
Corrected Total	136.803	34				

a. R Squared = .129 (Adjusted R Squared = -.058)

The result in Table 4 reveals that no significant difference existed in ACS among varied-ability male and female students taught Basic Science using CT, $F(2, 28) = 0.791, p(0.463) > 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore, not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Within creative teaching and lecture method, students' Abstract Creative-thinking Skill (ACS) were not significant different among varied-ability levels. However, students' ACS in the creative teaching was higher than those in the lecture method. With regards to field experience, the finding is not anomalous because students in the creative teaching were engaged through heightening anticipation, deepening expectation and keeping it going. They tickle their imaginations, acquire and create ideas, look beyond the information on the surface, give abstract description and find what was beneath all the resources. With ACS, Basic Science students construct their knowledge and use resources for productivity and if allowed it will enhance sustainability. This study agrees with Ng and Lee (2019) who found that the students tended to be good at producing a large number of relevant abstract thinking (abstractness of titles dimension), Özgenel et al. (2019) who found that the enriched workshop trainings given to the students have affected and developed the students' creative thinking skills (abstractness of

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

titles inclusively) positively. Similarly, this study concord with Marzieh and Nesa (2016) who found that the dimensions from creativity were significantly different between the two groups of bilingual students. The study also agrees with Midilli et al. (2022) who found that students who received pre-school education scored significantly higher than the students who did not receive pre-school education and Madar et al. (2019) who indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were at an excellent level.

Regarding students' ACS based on gender, no significant difference existed in ACS between male and female students with varied-ability levels taught Basic Science using creative teaching. This implies that, creative teaching on ACS is without gender disparity among different ability levels in Basic Science students. Following field experience, the finding is not bizarre since both boys and girls explored their ideas, constructed and used available resources for productivity and with expectation of more resources for future visions and/or sustainability through active involvement in creative teaching and learning processes. This study agrees with Midilli et al (2022) who found that there was no significant difference between the scores of the students in TTCT and gender. The study also agrees with Madar et al. (2019) indicated that the correlation among the three sets of marks for abstractness of titles were not significantly different based on gender. Dissimilarly, this study disagrees with Ulger and Morsunbul (2017) who found that there was a significant difference between male and female university students on creative thinking skills in favour of female. This difference may occur as the results of variation in the teaching method, location, and probably time and space.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that ACS among varied-ability students was enhanced without gender disparity, if Basic Science is taught using Creative Teaching.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were advanced:

1. Teachers not only at the upper basic school level, should be trained by the Federal, State Ministries of Education and other stakeholders through seminars, workshops on how to effectively utilize Creative Teaching.
2. Government through the Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers to maximize Creative Teaching lesson delivery.
3. Teacher training institutions in Nigeria should include constructive teaching strategies such as creative teaching in the teacher training programmes.
4. School proprietors, head and parents' teachers' association should provide materials/funds needed by teachers for creative teaching of Basic Science at basic education level.

References

- Ali, H., Ozovehe, A. & Dyaji, L. (2014). Impact of creative teaching on science pupils' academic performance. *IOSR Journal of Research and Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 4(6), 40-44. Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org
- Ayua G. A., Terhemba, W. K., & Ikyernum, G. S. (2022). Effect of creative teaching on creative thinking among different-ability upper-basic science students in Gboko Town. *African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*, 8(2), 182-188.
- Ayua, G. A. & Agbidye, A (2020). Effect of science-technology-society strategy on entrepreneurial creativity among upper-basic school students. *Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 4(9), 105-113. <http://nsukjste.com/>
- Ayua, G. A. & Eriba, J. O. (2023). Adapting creative teaching of Basic Science in special needs education: In J. A. Ademokoya, N. Akuma, E. O. Idiodi & S. O. A. Obih (Eds.), *Special Needs Education from the Lens of Interdisciplinary Dialogue, 1* (314 - 325). Owerri, Imo State: Citihall International.
- Bakhshi, H., Downing, J. M., Osborne, M. A., & Schneider, P. (2017). *The future of skills: Employment in 2030*. London: Pearson and Nesta. Retrieved from: <https://www.nesta.org.uk>
- Benue State Examination Board – BSEB. (2018). *Basic education certificate examination's grading system*. Makurdi, Nigeria: BSEB Office.
- Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME, (2018). *Examination grading system*. Makurdi, Nigeria: BSME Office.
- Bruner, J. S. (1960). *Towards a theory of instruction*. Cambridge: Harvard University.
- Danjuma, G. S. (2015). *Effects of collaborative and competitive learning strategies on upper-basic two students' interest and achievement in basic science*, PhD Science Education thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Effect of Creative-Teaching Strategy ... (Ayua et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072782>

- Gruszka, A. & Tang, M. (2017). The 4P's creativity model and its application in different fields. In M. Tang & C. H. Werner (Eds.), *Handbook of the Management of Creativity and Innovation: Theory and Practice* (51-71). Singapore: World Scientific.
- Hostetter, D. P. (2013). *Does homogenous ability grouping for high school honours English instruction benefit the high achiever?* PhD thesis, Seton Hall University, New Jersey, USA. Retrieved from [https://scholarship.shu.edu. \(11.11.2021\)](https://scholarship.shu.edu. (11.11.2021))
- Ikyernum, G. S. (2022). *Effect of teacher learner improvised material on creative and critical thinking among varied-ability upper basic science students in Makurdi Metropolis*. Unpublished BSc. (Ed) project, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.
- Irugalbandara, A. I. (2020). *Investigation of the development of creative thinking and adaptability skills through process drama techniques in junior secondary school students in Sri Lanka*. Thesis submitted to School of Early Childhood and Inclusive Education, Faculty of Education, Queensland University of Technology.
- Ismail, N., Desa, S., & Balakrishnan, B. (2018). Science Creative-Teaching design for science teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8 (4), 1235-1241. www.hrmars.com
- Madar, A. R., Sun, C. E. & Hamid, H. (2019). Facilitating Torrance Test of Creative Thinking Use in Malaysian TVET Research: The Initial Step of Inter-rater Reliability Determination. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 11 (1), 100–108. <https://doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2019.11.01.013>
- Maikano, S. (2016). *Impact of Computer-Assisted and Science Process Instructions on Retention and Performance in Biology Among Varied Abilities Secondary School Students in Kaduna, Nigeria*. PhD Science Education thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria.
- Marzieh, A. & Nesa, J. (2016). Comparison of Creativity Dimensions (Fluency, Flexibility, Elaboration, Originality) between Bilingual Elementary Students (Azari language-Kurdish language) in Urmia City – Iran. *The IAFOR International Conference on Language Learning: Official Conference Proceedings*. Islamic Azad University, Iran.
- McFinn, C. (2015). *Creative teaching and how to use them*. Retrieved 11.06.2023 from <http://www.captiummcfinn.com>
- Midilli, M., Özsoy, G. & Aslan, O. (2022). Examining of the Turkish gifted primary school students' creative thinking skills. *Journal of Gifted Education and Creativity*, 9(4), 417-431.
- Misutova, M. (2003). *Characterization of the new creative teaching model*. Retrieved 24th July, 2023 from <https://www.mtf.stuba.sk/buxus/docs/internetovy>
- Ng, A. W. Y., Lee, C. Y. (2019). Assessment of creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance tests of creative thinking. *5th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'19)*, Universitat Politècnica de València, València, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4995/HEAd19.2019.9051>
- Özgenel, M. Canpolat, O. Yağan, E. and Canlı, O. (2019). The effects of enriched workshop training given to pre-school students on creative thinking skills of students. *Problems of Education in the 21st century* 77 (5), 616-635.
- Peng, Y. (2019). *Effects of creativity instruction in science on creative thinking and science achievement in Chinese students*. University of Nevada, Las Vegas: University Libraries.
- Rosenstock, L., & Riordan, R. (2017). Changing the subject. In R. A. Beghetto, & J. C. Kaufman (Eds.), *Nurturing creativity in the classroom* (pp. 3-5). New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Schnapp, C. R. (2018). *A new model for creative education*. Master's Projects. Department of Creative Studies, Buffalo State University of New York. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.buffalostate.edu/creativeprojects/283>
- Scholastic Testing Service (2018). *Norms-Technical Manual for Figural Forms A and B*. Illinois, U.S.A.
- Terhemba, W. K. (2022). *Effect of creative teaching on creative and critical thinking among upper-basic school science students with different academic abilities*. B Sc. (Ed) project, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.
- Terhemba, W. K., Ayua, G. A., & Gamat, G. B. (2023). Effect of Creative-Teaching on Creative-Thinking-Originality Among Different-Ability Upper-Basic Science Students in Gboko Township. *African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education, AJSTME*, 9(3), 110-116.
- Ulger, K. & Morsunbul, U. (2017). The Differences in Creative Thinking: The Comparison of Male and Female Students. *The Online Journal of Counselling and Education*, 2016, 5(4), 1-12.